

Assessing the impact of agroecological practices on ecosystem services and crop productivity in open-field tomatoes in Greece

Vasileia Chatzaki, Anastasia Kokkari, Vaya Kati, Nikos Kouloussis, Dimitrios Koveos, Apostolos Kapranas

Faculty of Agriculture Forestry and Natural Environment, School of Agriculture, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, 54124 Thessaloniki, Greece

Abstract: Tomato is an important crop both globally and in Mediterranean countries. Agroecological farming practices aim to enhance functional biodiversity to support ecosystem services and reduce reliance on synthetic inputs. Our study investigates the impact of agroecological practices and boosting functional biodiversity, on the population dynamics of major tomato pests and important natural enemies, and the productivity of the tomato crop in open-field cultivation systems in Greece. Over three years we evaluated agroecological practices based on companion plants – phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia*) and buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum*) planted alongside tomatoes – and the application of the soil beneficial fungus, *Trichoderma harzianum* T22. In addition, we compared the agroecological approach with the conventional approach. Throughout the growing season, insect sampling was conducted in both the agroecological and the conventional experimental fields using Malaise traps and visual observations. Data collection focused on parasitoids, wasps, bees, syrphid flies (Syrphidae), and predatory insects of the family Miridae. Simultaneously, populations of the main tomato pests were recorded. In the agroecological system, the individual and combined effects of the companion plants and fungus on tomato plant physiology and growth were also assessed. Our results suggest that the agroecological approach enhanced functional biodiversity, increased the abundance and diversity of beneficial insects, and reduced pest pressure, while also boosting tomato growth and crop productivity. This study aims to develop an agroecological tomato cultivation model that utilizes and strengthens functional biodiversity in order to enhance ecosystem services and crop productivity with minimal inputs.

Key words: agroecology, tomato, companion plants, soil symbionts, conservation biological control, pests, yield

Introduction

Tomato is a key crop worldwide, particularly in the Mediterranean Basin. Its market value in the EU amounts to approximately 7 billion euros, with Italy, Spain, Greece, and Portugal accounting for over 90 % of EU production (Eurostat, 2025). Regardless of the cultivation system (open-field or greenhouse) or the duration of the production cycle, increasing quantities of external inputs – such as pesticides, fertilizers, and herbicides – are required to ensure satisfactory levels of crop protection and yield. Major insect pests, spearheaded by *Tuta absoluta*, whiteflies, and mites, cause significant yield losses in tomato crops and substantially increase production costs (Wakil et al., 2018).

Agroecological approaches that focus on the conservation and enhancement of functional biodiversity, both above- and belowground, aim to increase and exploit ecosystem services such as pest regulation, nutrient cycling, and pollination, offering a potential alternative to the use of external synthetic inputs (Palomo-Campesino et al., 2022). However, their adoption relies on their validation experimentally.

Plant diversity in non-crop habitats can lead to reduced herbivore abundance and crop damage, accompanied by increased diversity and abundance of beneficial taxa that suppress economically important insect pests (Wan et al., 2020). The establishment of flowering plants is a key component of habitat management through plant diversity integration within the context of conservation biological control (Gurr et al., 2017). In addition, bottom-up effects –such as the disruption of host-finding and feeding behavior of herbivorous insects – play an important role in shaping pest population dynamics in agroecosystems. However, two critical factors must be considered: first, companion plants may also serve as hosts for insects and pathogens that can negatively affect the main crop; second, increases in natural enemy assemblages resulting from enhanced plant diversity are not always directly linked to effective pest suppression.

Several studies have documented increased biodiversity of beneficial pollinators and entomophagous insects promoted by diverse flowering plant mixtures, along with the ecosystem services they provide (Balzan et al., 2017; Kati et al., 2021). Popular flowering plants that provide food resources to beneficial insects and pollinators include, among others, alyssum (*Lobularia maritima* (L.) Desv., Brassicaceae), buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum* Moench., Polygonaceae), coriander (*Coriandrum sativa* L., Apiaceae) and phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia* Benth., Hydrophyllaceae) (Pontin et al., 2006). Nevertheless, significant knowledge gaps remain regarding pest population dynamics and crop productivity under such systems.

Furthermore, the conservation and enhancement of soil biodiversity, particularly beneficial soil symbionts, can promote plant growth and strengthen plant defenses. Fungi of the genus *Trichoderma* are among the most extensively studied plant-associated microorganisms and are known to trigger induced resistance against a wide range of pests and diseases (Woo et al., 2022; Flors et al., 2024). Of particular relevance to tomato cultivation is the ability of *Trichoderma* spp. to enhance crop productivity and resistance to the leaf-mining pest *T. absoluta* in greenhouse systems (Minchev et al., 2024, 2026).

In this study, we implement agroecological practices in open-field tomato crops and evaluate both their individual and combined effects. Specifically, we assess how these practices, alone and in synergy, influence functional biodiversity, insect pest populations, and tomato plant growth and productivity.

Materials and methods

Experimental plots

Activities took place in a conventional open-field tomato crop in Epanomi, Thessaloniki, and an experimental tomato field in Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) farm during 2023-2025. The two crops were 15 km apart. The conventional commercial field encompassed an area of ca. 30 × 15 m and there was frequent use of pesticides and fertilizers. In the AUTH farm, the experimental tomato field had three treatment plots: 1) tomato plot with phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia*) as companion plant and application of *Trichoderma harzianum* T22, 2) tomato plot with buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum*) as companion plant and application of *Trichoderma harzianum* T22 and 3) control tomato plot. Within the two companion plant treatments, *T. harzianum* T22 was applied to half of the tomato plants to assess the individual

and combined effects of companion plant proximity (plants located close to or far from companion plants) and fungal application on arthropod communities, pest populations, and crop development. Each plot containing companion plants measured 12 × 3 m. Adjacent tomato plots measured 10 × 12 m, with a total of 216 tomato plants established. The internal control plot was 5 × 7 m, with 70 tomato plants. No pesticides or fertilizers were applied in the AUTH farm. Crops in the two fields consisted of determinate tomato varieties (Mountain fresh in AUTH farm and Zinnia in Epanomi).

Evaluation of functional biodiversity

Throughout the growing season over all three years (2023-2025), insect sampling was conducted in both the agroecological AUTH farm and the conventional commercial fields using Malaise traps to compare the diversity of Hymenoptera and Syrphidae. For the years 2024-2025 we also compared populations of beneficial Miridae between the conventional and agroecological fields and furthermore, within the two agroecological plots with the companion plants (plot 1 and 2) to assess the effect of the companion plant and the beneficial fungi and its combination. Lastly in year 2025 we did visual observation of mainly pollinators for 10 consecutive days during the flowering period of the companion plants at the AUTH farm.

Monitoring pest populations

Key pests such as *Tuta absoluta*, whiteflies (primarily *Bemisia* spp.) and tetranychid mites were monitored every 10-15 days across all experimental tomato plots.

Assessing treatments on yield and quality of the crop

Growth and productivity of tomato plants were evaluated in the two agroecological plots and the internal control plot in the AUTH farm by recording fruit weight and quality of the first fruits reaching harvest and classifying them into three size- and quality-based categories for the years 2024 and 2025.

Results and discussion

First analyses indicate that agroecological practices substantially influenced functional biodiversity, pest dynamics, and crop performance. Hymenoptera communities in the AUTH farm where the two agroecological plots were located showed greater family richness and a more even taxonomic distribution compared to the conventional field, suggesting enhanced ecosystem stability. Syrphidae abundance was consistently higher in agroecological plots, particularly during fruit development. Miridae populations were lower in the conventional system across all samplings within the crop season, whereas in agroecological plots they were initially more abundant near companion plants and gradually dispersed into the crop, indicating the role of companion plants as reservoirs for beneficial arthropods. Companion plants supported distinct insect visitor assemblages: phacelia was primarily visited by honeybees ($\approx 60\%$ of visits), followed by syrphids, while buckwheat was mainly visited by syrphids, wasps and wild bees.

Tuta absoluta populations persisted and increased toward harvest despite continuous pesticide applications in the conventional field, while no whitefly or mite infestations were recorded in this system. In contrast, no infestations of *T. absoluta* or whiteflies were observed in the AUTH farm encompassing the agroecological plots. Spider mite infestations occurred in agroecological plots; however, in plants treated with *Trichoderma harzianum* T22, mite populations were significantly reduced, indicating a suppressive effect of the beneficial fungus.

Regarding crop productivity and quality, the two agroecological plots consistently showed higher tomato yield and fruit number per plant compared to the internal control. Moreover, in 2025, fruit quality improved in the agroecological crop with phacelia, with a higher proportion of fruits classified in the highest quality category. Our results suggest that agroecological practices enhanced functional biodiversity, improved biological regulation of pests, increased yield and improved fruit quality. The combined use of companion plants and *T. harzianum* T22 appeared to act synergistically, contributing to greater stability and resilience of the tomato agroecosystem and supporting agroecology as a sustainable approach to tomato crop management.

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